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Potential of Strawberry Fruit (*Fragaria Vesca L*), Coffee (*Coffea*), and Honey (Honeybee) as Facial Mask to Smooth the Face

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Abstract

Facial masks are skin care products used on the face, one of the benefits of facial masks is that the face looks more moisturized. This study aims to determine how the potential of strawberry fruit (*Fragaria Vesca L.*), coffee (*Coffea*), and honey (Honeybee) to smooth the face. The research method used is experimental research method. The experimental method is a study conducted to find the effect of something that is done intentionally by the researcher. The results of the analysis of the face mask are the color of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 100\%$. The aroma of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 100\%$. The texture of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 50\%$, $N = 12.5\%$, $KS = 12.5\%$, and $TS = 25\%$. The stickiness of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 62.5\%$, $N = 12.5\%$, $KS = 05$, and $TS = 25\%$. This face mask is suitable for use on the skin because it can smooth our facial skin.

Keyword: Face Mask; Strawberry; Coffee

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Page 197-204

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INTRODUCTION

Skin is the outermost protective part that lines most of the human body. The facial skin is the most sensitive part of the skin, so it is more susceptible to problems than others. Improper facial skin care can cause new facial skin problems or even worsen previous problems (Shinta Dewi, 2023). Facial skin is the main part that shows a person's health. Facial skin that looks dull can be caused by various factors, one of which is the accumulation of dead skin cells. Therefore, many people use face masks to maintain the health of their skin. Facial masks are beauty masks that are gels, pastes, and powders that are applied to clean, smooth, moisturize, and tighten facial skin (Rudi, 2021; Bahri, 2019; Seroja, 2019; Nugroho, 2020; Aida, 2020).

Facial cosmetics can be obtained in various dosage forms. Facial masks are very popular beauty care cosmetics to improve skin quality. A peel-off face mask is one type of face mask that has the advantage of being easily removed or lifted, like an elastic membrane. Peel-off face masks are formulated with active substances, PVA bases, softening agents, moisturizers, preservatives, surfactants, and fragrances. Based on this background, it is necessary to optimize the formulation of peel-off gel mask preparations to obtain preparations of high quality (Munidar, 2024; Paull, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024; Johan, 2024). To obtain a preparation formulation of good quality, it can be done by evaluating organoleptics, pH, viscosity, spreadability, drying time, appearance, film thickness, and stability profile. A peel-off face mask preparation with good quality can be seen from the drying time, which is influenced by the concentration of EtOH, gelatin, and glycerin, while the ease of use of the preparation related to viscosity is influenced by the concentration of PVA, carbomer, gelatin, and glycerin, and film formation performance is influenced by the concentration of PVA.

Strawberry (*Fragaria Vesca L.*) is one of the fruits that is good for making face masks because it contains salicylic acid, which is a type of beta-hydroxy acid that helps tighten the skin, silica, and vitamins B, C, E, and K. With the content of tertebar substances, strawberry fruit is able to brighten and pamper the skin. Strawberry fruit masks are excellent for all skin types. The efficacious active substance in strawberry fruit that has the highest antioxidant potential is ellagic acid. In strawberries, there is ellagic acid of around 40mg in 100g of strawberry fruit (Nowak, 2006). Anthocyanin compounds give strawberry fruit a red color that functions as a very strong antioxidant (Ferdiansyah, 2016).

Coffee (coffee) is one of the ingredients that is suitable for use as a face mask material because coffee contains 0.2% polyphenol compounds, which are useful as antioxidants in facial skin. Coffee beans are very good for removing dead skin cells, moisturizing, and softening the face (Wulandari et al., 2019). In addition to strawberries and coffee, honey (HoneyBee) is also very often used for facial mask ingredients because honey is hygroscopic, which makes it easy to absorb water from the air and its surroundings because it can be used as a humectant and helps maintain skin. In addition, honey nourishes internal epithelial tissue and facilitates circulation so as to prevent dry skin. In addition, honey also has various vitamins, namely vitamins A, B1, B2, B3, B5, B6, D, K, and E, and minerals such as calcium, sodium, potassium, magnesium, and iron, as well as iodine salts and even radium. All types of minerals are constituent elements of the earth or soil.

In research (Ni Wayan Sasri Septiari, 2014), Research conducted by Ni Wayan Sasri Septiari in 2014 on the Effect of the Proportion of Strawberry Puree (*Fragaria vesca l.*) and Tapioca on the Quality of Traditional Face Masks from Cosmetology Education, Faculty of

Engineering, Surabaya State University. This type of research is experimental. The independent variables in the proportion of strawberry puree and tapioca flour are (25g: 75g); (50g: 50g); (75g: 25g), while the dependent variable is traditional face masks through physical properties, the number of ingredients, and chemical content.

The purpose of this research is to determine the potential of strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L.), coffee (*Coffea*), and honey (HoneyBee) as ingredients for making face masks. The benefits of this research include moisturizing and smoothing the face and becoming more frequent in using face masks regularly to maintain healthy facial skin.

METHOD

The research method used is experimental. Experimental research is a study conducted to find the effect of something that is done intentionally by the researcher. The type of research conducted is qualitative. The population of this study will be tested on all students, teachers, and misses at MTsN Banda Aceh. The sample of students amounted to 1 person, while the teacher amounted to 1 person, and the miss amounted to 6 people. The research method used is the experimental method. According to Hamdayana (2017) (125), the experimental method is a way of presenting students with an opportunity with an opportunity to experiment by experiencing something that they have learned. Data collection techniques and tools will be given as an attachment to the panelists, namely Appendix 1.

The processing method carried out is to give a cup containing a face mask to be applied to the face. After trying, the researcher will give a questionnaire to the panelists and interview their opinions about the color, texture, aroma, and stickiness of the mask. After being given the questionnaire, the panelists filled it out on a Likert scale. Which consists of positive statements $SS = 3$ $S = 2$ $TS = 1$, and negative statements $SS = 1$ $S = 2$ AND $TS = 3$. Then, the researcher will interview the panelists about the results of the face mask trial in terms of color, aroma, texture, and adhesiveness. The analysis carried out in this study is a percentage calculation with the organoleptic test with a hedonic scale of face masks through the percentage of color, texture, aroma, and adhesiveness.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

This mask has raw materials that contain substances that are beneficial to the face. For example, strawberries and honey have vitamin C, and coffee contains antioxidants. In this study, there are several elements that will be tested, such as color, aroma, texture, and adhesiveness. There are 8 people who will be tested, namely:

Table 1. Percentage of color in face masks

Answer	Number of answers	Answer score	Percentage
Like	8	4	100
Neutral	0	3	0
Not really like	0	2	0
Dislike	0	1	0

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted that the color of this face mask is preferred with a percentage of $S = 100\%$, $N = 0\%$, $KS = 0\%$, and $TS = 0\%$.

Table 2. Percentage of aroma in face masks

Answer	Number of answers	Answer score	Percentage
Like	8	4	100
Neutral	0	3	0
Not really like	0	2	0
Dislike	0	1	0

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted that the aroma of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 100\%$ and $N = 0\%$. $KS=0\%$, and $TS=0\%$.

Table 3. Percentage of texture in face masks

Answer	Number of answers	Answer score	Percentage
Like	4	4	50
Neutral	1	3	12.5
Not really like	1	2	12.5
Dislike	2	1	25

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted that the texture of the face mask has a percentage of $S = 50\%$, $N = 12.5\%$, $KS = 12.5\%$, and $TS = 25\%$.

Table 4. Percentage of adhesion on face masks.

Answer	Number of answers	Answer score	Percentage
Like	5	4	62.5
Neutral	1	3	12.5
Not really like	0	2	0
Dislike	2	1	25

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted that the stickiness of the face mask has a percentage of S = 62.5%, N = 12.5%. KS = 0% and TS = 25%.

From the above research, there have been many positive and negative comments because the texture is still quite rough, so it is uneven when applied to the face, and its adhesiveness still requires additional honey and coffee so that the adhesiveness of the mask is not too liquid when applied to the panelists' faces. The results of the analysis of the face mask are the color of the face mask with a percentage of S = 100%, N = 0%, KS = 0%, and TS = 0%. While the aroma on the face mask has a percentage of S = 100%, N = 0%, KS = 0%, and TS = 0%. Texture on face masks has a percentage of S = 50%, N = 12.5%, KS = 12.5%, and TS = 25%. And the stickiness of the face mask had a percentage of S = 62.5%, N = 12.5%, KS = 0%, and TS = 25%. There were panelists who did not like the rough texture and liquid stickiness so much that it could not be applied to the face.

This research is the same as Octavia (2008) which states that strawberry fruit is often used as a mask material because this fruit contains many vitamins and minerals that can provide nutrition to the skin. Suranny and Wagino (2019) state that coffee can remove dead skin cells, shrink blackheads, and overcome black flecks on the face.

CONCLUSION

Based on testing that is in accordance with the method, this mask deserves to be a mask that can make the skin a little brighter and more moisturized. For the physical form, the panelists really liked the mask, but not the stickiness, which was too liquid and could not stick to the face. If the texture and adhesiveness of this face mask are developed, the results received by the panelists will be even better.

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